

NOTES

Ligand Association of *N,N*-Dimethylaniline with Uranium(IV) Chloride

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LIGAND association plays a prominent role in the synthesis of organoactinide compounds. The stability of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{UCl}_3\cdot\text{DME}^1$ and $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{UCl}_3\cdot 2\text{THF}^2$ are attributed to the coordination of THF or DME to uranium (THF=tetrahydrofuran, DME=1,2-dimethoxyethane). During our attempts to make trialkyls of the type, $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{UR}_3$, we found that UCl_4 reacted with *N,N*-dimethylaniline. On the basis of analytical and spectral data the stoichiometry of the resulting complex is assigned to be $\text{UCl}_4\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere using a double manifold, connected to a vacuum pump and a cylinder of nitrogen. The solvents used were dried by reported methods³. Hexachloropropene (Koch-Light) was used without further purification. *N,N*-Dimethylaniline was distilled under reduced pressure (40°/–1 mm) and stored in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

$\text{UCl}_4\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$: UCl_4 was prepared⁴ by the action of hexachloropropene on uranium trioxide obtained by hydrolysis of uranyl acetate or by the thermal decomposition of uranyl nitrate. The amount of uranium was estimated by titration with Ce^{IV} ⁵. Chlorine was estimated by removing the U^{IV} by precipitation with NaOH and back-titration with ammonium thiocyanate⁵ (Found: U, 62.5; Cl, 36.4. UCl_4 calcd. for: U, 62.7; Cl, 37.3%). To a solution of UCl_4 (0.5 g, 1.32 mmol) in THF (~20 ml), *N,N*-dimethylaniline (1 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred for 12 h. The solvent was then removed in vacuum. The resulting air-sensitive blue-green solid was washed with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum (Found: U, 38.3; Cl, 23.1. $\text{UCl}_4\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ calcd. for: U, 39.6; Cl, 22.8%).

The ir sample was made as nujol in a polythene bag filled with nitrogen and recorded using a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer. The visible spectrum was taken on a Jasco UVIDEC-430B spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Estimation of chloride was done in a manner analogous to the procedure used for that of UCl_4 . Uranium in the complex was estimated by the addition of a known excess of cerium(IV) sulphate to a solution of the complex followed by titration against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate without using any indicator. A sharp end-point from green to red was observed. Two-electron oxidation of amines by Ce^{IV} is well known especially in presence of metal ions⁶. We assumed oxidation of U^{IV} to UO_2^{II} and tertiaryamine to amine oxide. Thus a six-electron oxidation takes place when $\text{UCl}_4\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ reacts with Ce^{IV} . Direct titration of the solution of the complex with $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ using ferroin indicator was unsuccessful since the solution remained red even beyond the equivalence-point and no sharp end-point could be detected.

The ir spectra of the blue-green solid reveal peaks (Table I) due to *N,N*-dimethylaniline in which some of the peaks are shifted to higher

TABLE I—IR FREQUENCIES AND SELECTED ASSIGNMENTS FOR $\text{UCl}_4\cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$

Frequency* cm ⁻¹	Assignments
3 450–3 225	Aromatic C–H str
3 100–2 900	Aliphatic C–H str
1 599s	Aromatic C–H str
1 418m	sp ³ –C–N str
1 195, 1 180, 1 150w	—
1 100, 1 055, 1 025, 990w	—
765s	Aromatic C–H out-of-plane bending
750w	Aromatic C–C out-of-plane bending
575s	U–N
530w	—
475w	U–N

*s=strong, w=weak, m=medium.

frequencies. Complexation is indicated by the shift of peak due to sp³ C–N stretch which occurs at 1 345 cm⁻¹ in *N,N*-dimethylaniline⁶ and at 1 418 cm⁻¹ in the product. Similarly, aromatic C–H (765 cm⁻¹) and C–C (750 cm⁻¹) out-of-plane vibrations show pronounced shifts. The corresponding peaks appear at 747 and 688 cm⁻¹ in the free amine⁶. The new peaks at 575 and 475 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of U–N bond in the complex. Similar vibrations are observed at 570 and 480 cm⁻¹ for $\text{Cp}_3\text{UNC}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CHP}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{CH}_3$ ⁷ (Cp= η -cyclopentadienyl) and at 535 and 490 cm⁻¹ for UCl_3NH_3 ⁸.

The visible spectra of the complex in water reveal absorption maxima at 640 (strong), 598, 478, 464 and 452 nm. Strong absorptions around 600 nm have been previously noticed for $\eta^5\text{-(C}_5\text{H}_5)_3\text{UCl}^{10}$ and several other uranium(IV) complexes¹¹. The presence of uranium(IV) in the complex is thus indicated. Owing to the insolubility of the complex in the common solvents we could neither get the conductivity and nmr data nor determine its molecular weight employing the usual methods.

References

1. L. DORETTI, P. ZANELLA, G. FARAGLIA and S. FALRSCHINI, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1972, **43**, 339.
2. K. W. BAGNALL and J. EDWARDS, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1974, **80**, C14.
3. A. J. GORDON and R. A. FORD, "The Chemist's Companion—A Handbook of Practical Data, Techniques and References", Wiley, New York, 1972, p. 429.
4. J. A. HERMANN and J. F. SUTTLE, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, **5**, 143.
5. J. BASSETT, R. C. DENNEY, G. H. JEFFERY and J. MENDHAM, "Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 4th ed., Longmans, London, 1978, pp. 342, 370.
6. R. C. BANK, E. R. MALJEKA and G. MEHLER, "Introductory Problems in Spectroscopy", Benjamin, Mento Park, 1980, p. 100.
7. K. PANCHANATHESWARAN, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Hawaii, 1984.
8. J. SELBIN, M. SCHÖBER and J. D. ORTEGO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1385.
9. M. N. RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **29**, 1040.
10. L. T. RENOIDS and G. WILKINSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, **2**, 246.
11. K. W. BAGNALL in "Organometallics of 'f' Elements", eds. T. G. MARKS and R. D. FISCHER, Reidel, Dordrecht, 1979, p. 232.

Characterisation of a New Complex of $\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$ (TSTI) with ZrOCl_2 by XRD Spectrum

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SURVEY of literature reveals that complexes of TSTI ($\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$)^{1,2}, except with silver³ have not been synthesised and studied so far. Therefore, the complex of TSTI with ZrOCl_2 was prepared and the results of investigations are reported here.

Experimental

TSTI ($\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$) was prepared by methanolic SnCl_2 reduction⁴ of S_4N_4 . The formation of TSTI was established by its m.p., molecular weight, ir and electronic spectra. The complex of TSTI with ZrOCl_2 (anhydrous) was synthesised by

refluxing equimolar amount of TSTI and ZrOCl_2 (anhydrous) in DMF for ~48 h with constant mechanical stirring. The resulting light brown product was separated, washed with DMF to free it from unreacted TSTI and ZrOCl_2 , and then dried in vacuum.

The complex was analysed using gravimetric and absorption spectral techniques⁶. Its molecular weight was determined by viscosity method. Ir (KBr) and electronic (reflectance) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 and VSU-22 spectrophotometers, respectively, at 300 K. X-Ray powder diffraction spectra were recorded on a XRD-6 GM-11 diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (λ 1.5418 Å) as a source of radiation.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complex (Found : Zr, 25.0 ; N, 15.0 ; H, 1.1 ; Cl, 19.6 ; O, 4.3%) and molecular weight 1135, lead to the molecular formula of the complex as $(\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{ZrOCl}_2)_3$. It has m.p. 228°, and its colour darkens.

On the basis of available literature, its ir spectrum is interpreted and compared to that of TSTI and strong absorption bands at 719s and 765s cm^{-1} due to two free S-N vibrations and two other frequencies at 1 110 and 1 162 cm^{-1} (shifted to higher region), indicate the presence of two S-N bands having coordinated nitrogen. The peaks at 1 370–1 605 cm^{-1} correspond to N-H bands. The broad band at 2 885–3 420 cm^{-1} is due to δ_{NH} showing hydrogen bonding between N atom of $\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$ and Cl atom of ZrOCl_2 . The ir spectra clearly indicate that $\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$ is linked to ZrOCl_2 by bidentate bridging of Zr atom through coordination by N terminals of $\text{S}_4\text{N}_4\text{H}_4$ ring, forming a coordinated trimer (Fig. 1).

Further, its electronic spectra reveal three peaks at 360, 300 and 289 nm. The peak at 289 nm is due to charge transfer transition in ZrOCl_2 caused by its electrovalent character. The presence of charge transfer transition is also supported by the ratio $\nu_3/\nu_2=0.83$ (<1). The value calculated for the oscillator strength ($f=1.12 \times 10^{-4}$), suggests that the 360 and 300 nm transitions are spin-allowed laporte forbidden transition. The values determined from its electronic spectrum, for the band gap energy (ΔE 0.69 eV) and conductivity ($\lambda_\alpha=3.2 \times 10^{-12} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) indicate the semiconductive nature of the complex which may be due to the presence of holes in its internal array.

To arrive at conclusive geometrical structure of the complex, Miller indices I/I_0 and $d(\text{Å})$ are calculated from its X-ray powder diffraction spectrum which is obtained over 2θ range 6–60°. The values of I/I_0 show a gradation supporting the presence of holes and semiconductivity of the complex and the fall in intensity suggests that complex is less crystalline. The d values which coincide

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